

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE & PRACTICE AMONG NURSES REGARDING CATHETER ASSOCIATED URINARY TRACT INFECTION (CAUTI)

¹Usma Sharif, ²Misbah Sharif, ³Donia Abbas¹Charge nurse, Chaudhary Pervaiz Elahi Institute Of Cardiology Wazirabad²Charge Nurse, Lady Wallingdon Hospital, Lahore³Assistant Nursing Instructor, College of Nursing and Midwifery Fatima Jinnah University
Lahore**Abstract:**

Introduction: Urinary catheterization is one of the most common procedures performed in hospitals specifically, in the intensive care units and is associated with a high risk for acquired urinary tract infections. More than 70% of acquired urinary tract infections are due to catheter use.

Objective: "Assessment of knowledge and practice among nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection at Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore.

Materials & methods: It was descriptive cross-sectional study in nature in which 92 nurses recruited. Self-administered questionnaires were used to collect the data from the participants.

Results: In the population of 1200 nurses only 300 included in the study having age 21 to 60 years old. Overall result findings showed that 45.65.50% participants having good knowledge and remaining 54.35% had poor. In contrast, 48.66% participants reported adequate practices and 51.33% had inadequate practices.

Conclusion: In conclusion, lack of knowledge found among the study participants regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection. As compared to knowledge practices regarding CAUTI were little bit better among respondents. Age, professional experience, working unit had direct association with the knowledge and practices of study participants. Overall, lack of knowledge and poor practices reported among the nurses of hospital may cause to increase the LOS (length of stay) and cost of not only the hospital but also healthcare department of the Pakistan.

Keywords: CAUTI (Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection), Association for Professionals in Infection Control (APIC), nurses, knowledge, practices etc.

Corresponding author:**Usma Sharif,**

Charge nurse,

Chaudhary Pervaiz Elahi Institute Of Cardiology,
Wazirabad

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press *Usma Sharif et al., Assessment Of Knowledge & Practice Among Nurses Regarding Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection (CAUTI), Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(10).*

INTRODUCTION

Globally, there has been challenges and renewal interesting researches to reduce the incidence of CAUTI (Catheter-associated urinary tract infection) (Parker et al., 2017). On the other

hand, device-associated healthcare associated infection DA-HAI data and published studies to certain devices were limited in (Gaid et al., 2017). Nurses were the primary healthcare providers responsible for inserting and

maintaining urinary catheters, as well as the production of desired outcomes by which they followed the available guidelines, protocols, and standards during catheter insertion and catheter cares (Martin J., 2012). Nurses were considered as the primary healthcare providers who were responsible for inserting and maintaining of urinary catheters, as well as production of desired outcomes (Banks, et al., 2016). Nurses played an important role in urinary catheter insertion,

The knowledge and practice of nurses towards prevention of CAUTIs was poor in developing countries (Algarni et al., 2019). Nurses were also accountable to acquire appropriate knowledge and practices of catheter care that will prevent UTIs (Al Nasser et al., 2016). Therefore, nurses should have adequate knowledge regarding infection control in the use of urethral catheters and their practice must be adhered to healthcare setting's guidelines on infection control (Opina & Oducado, 2014).

The nurses were least knowledgeable about different approaches to catheterization and specimen collecting methods followed by proper urethral catheter maintenance and finally, considerations and techniques for catheter insertion. Regarding considerations and techniques for catheter insertion, the majority of nurses in this study knew that Silicone was preferable than Teflon-coated and latex catheter materials in reducing the risk of encrustation for long-term catheterized patients who have a frequent obstruction (Opina and Oducado, 2014).

It was reported that 60% of nurses did not realize that using alcohol hand sanitizer was comparable to hand washing in preventing CAUTI (Opina and Oducado, 2014). In another study reported that 70% of nurses knew that using alcohol hand sanitizer was comparable to hand washing in preventing CAUTI (Shah et al., 2017).

It was showed that 55.7% of nurses mistakenly considered that antimicrobial prophylaxis offered greater benefit, while only 44.3% considered that antimicrobial prophylaxis did not provide greater benefit (Shah et al., 2017). In a study revealed that 31.9% of nurses in Turkey while taking culture or sample, aspirate the urine from the needleless sampling port with syringe after cleansing the port with a disinfectant (Kose et al., 2016).

There was low level 64.52% of knowledge regarding CAUTI found among the nurses (Mukakamanzi, 2017). It was found that near to half of participants in Pakistan had poor knowledge towards CAUTI prevention (Shehzadi et al., 2018). The study found that 88.2% of

nurses performed hand washing before urinary catheter insertion (Kose et al., 2016).

It was found that 100% of the nurses performed hand washing before and after insertion (Mukakamanzi, 2017) while contradicted with Shehab (2017), who found that only 36% of nurses performed hand washing before and after insertion. It was indicated that 73.3% of nurses had correct practices in keeping the collecting bag and tube free from kinking (Opina and Oducado, 2014).

It was reported that 94.3% of nurses had correct practices in keeping the collecting bag and tube free from kinking (Mukakamanzi, 2017). Regarding nurses' practices after catheter insertion, more than half of nurses incorrectly contradicted with (Opina and Oducado, 2014), who found that 100 % of nurses placed the collecting bag below the bladder. In addition, it was indicated that 90.6% of the nurses placed the collecting bag below the bladder and stated that 90.6% of nurses wearing of gown during any manipulation of the indwelling catheter (Mukakamanzi, 2017).

It was found that there was a significant positive relationship between knowledge and practices of nurses regarding the prevention of CAUTI (Zachariah, 2016). Another study conducted in Iran regarding CAUTI and showed there was a positive relationship between knowledge and practice, which showed that with enhanced knowledge, the practice can be enhanced (Kalantarzadeh et al., 2014). The evidence indicated that factors such as the availability of resources and presence of guidelines in the health facility have a positive impact on the knowledge and practice of nurses towards prevention of CAUTIs (Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infections) (Zegeye AF, Kassahun CW, Temechu YZ, 2021). In view of the above current study carried out to assess knowledge and practices among nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection at Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore.

1.1. Problem statement

Catheter associated urinary tract infections is the most common HCAI (Hospital Associated Infection) related to prolonged use of urinary catheter and leading to increased length of hospital stay and morbidity. Surprisingly, in healthcare settings located in developing countries, urine bags are kept in the patient's trouser pockets or in their bed so blocking the drainage systems and increasing the risk of CAUTI. Another issues is that patients stay with the urinary catheter even when it is no longer needed and catheter care, maintenance and timely removal are very poor Also, in some healthcare

facility, nurses are not aware that the patients had a urinary catheter, or urine bags are on the floor or in the patient's bed or regular emptying is not done timely. This make the main risk factors for developing CAUTI among many hospitalized patients. Although this is the case, healthcare system have to provide reassurance that the care will be delivered safely and efficiently to prevent disease related vulnerability. Even though many efforts have been made to prevention CAUTI, the infection continue to rise counting and most of the time due to inadequate knowledge about basic catheter care practices especially among nurses Thus the researcher has an interest to conduct a study to assess the knowledge and practices of nurses towards the prevention of those infections especially among patients with a urinary catheter.

1.2. Significance of the study

The burden of CAUTI affect the individual patients and the health care system as a whole. Nurses are responsible for providing assessment and management of patients including the responsibility for sterile insertion of urinary catheters, needed daily maintenance, and timely catheter removal to prevent catheter associated UTI. This research study assessed the nurses knowledge and practices towards CAUTI prevention and the research results will contribute to nursing educational needs, practices, and further research contributing to an increase in the quality of care and improvement of the critical patient's outcomes. Concerning management and administration, it is hoped that this study will serve to inform the development of context based and evidence based guidelines. Apart from that this research will play a role in education whereby the study hopes to inform context based content for nursing curriculum in the country especially clinical learning activities including continuing Professional Development (CPD).

1.3. Objectives

The objective of the current research work as follows:

- ⊙ To determine nurse's level of knowledge regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection.
- ⊙ To compare nurse's level of knowledge with the practices regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection.

1.4. Research questions

1. What was the level of knowledge among nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection?
2. What was the level of practices as compared to knowledge among nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection?

1.5. Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There was no statistical significant relationship between demographic data and knowledge, practices regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection among nurses.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_A): There was statistical significant relationship between demographic data and knowledge, practices regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection among nurses.

1.6. Definition of key terms

⊙ Catheter associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI)

It is an infection of the urinary tract caused by a tube (urinary catheter that has been placed to drain urine from bladder. The urinary tract consists of the kidneys, ureters (tubes joining the kidneys to the bladder), and urethra (tube leading from the bladder to the outside of the body).

⊙ Knowledge

Facts, information and skills acquired through experience or education; the theoretical or practical understanding of a subject.

⊙ Practice

The actual application or use of an idea, belief, or method, as opposed to theories relating to it.

METHODOLOGY:

3.1. Study design:

Cross-sectional study design (observational design) was adopted because the data was collected from many different individuals at a single point. Basically, the study was descriptive (Quantitative) in nature.

3.2. Study setting:

The study was conducted at Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore.

3.3. Duration of study:

The study completed in 6 weeks (from 15-08-2022 to 30-09-2022).

3.4. Study Population:

Nurses of Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore.

3.5. Sample size & sampling

In the population of 1200 nurses following sample was drawn for the study by using listed below formulae:

$N = \text{Population} = 1200; n = \text{Sample Size};$
 $E = \text{Margin error} = 0.05$

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(E)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1200}{1 + 1200(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1200}{1 + 1200(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1200}{1 + 3}$$

$$n = \frac{1200}{4}$$

$$n = 300$$

Thus a more suitable sample of n= 300 considered for the study.

3.6. Sampling Technique:

Convenient sampling technique.

3.7. Eligibility Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Nurses age range 21-60 years old included in the study.
- Only female nurses included in the study.
- Nurses having qualification e.g., Diploma in General Nursing, Post RN, and Generic Nursing included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Nurses less than 21 years age excluded from the study.
- Male nurses excluded from the study.
- Nurses other than qualification e.g., Diploma in General Nursing, Post RN and Generic Nursing excluded from the study.

3.8. Data collection method

Self-administered questionnaire were used to collect the data from the study participants.

3.9. Ethical consideration

This study was approved by the ethical review committee of the institution and performed in accordance with the principles of Committee. To ensure their voluntary participation, inform consent was obtained from all the participants. All participants had autonomy to withdraw their consent at any time during the stipulated period of the study.

3.10. Data Analysis

The descriptive data statistically investigated using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social

Sciences) version 20. Results inferred through frequencies and percentages to check the accuracy of data. Data was represented in graphs, tables and MS excel used to check the accuracy of data.

RESULTS:

Urinary catheterization is one of the most common procedures performed in hospitals especially in intensive care units. The urinary catheter is considered as a single biggest risk factor for acquired urinary tract infections (UTIs), and more than 80% of all acquired UTIs are attributable to catheter use. Aim of the current study was to assess knowledge and practices among nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection at Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore. There were 1200 nurses appeared in the research and 300 considered for the study and rest of the nurses excluded as they didn't meet the criterion of the study.

In the population of 1200 nurses only 300 female participants included in the study having age 21 years old to 60 years old. 48.66% (n=146) having age group (21-30) years; 25.00% (n=75) belonged to (31-40) years; 21.66% (n=65) had an age group of (41-50) years and remaining 4.66% (n=14) belonged to (51-60) years old. Mean age of the participants was \bar{X} = 35.61 years old; Standard deviation = \pm 9.0 as depicted in the (Table no. 4.1. & figure no. 4.1.).

Now coming towards the professional experience of the participants 26.66% (n=80) having 1 to 3 years; 43.33% (n=130) having 4 to 6 years; 12.33% (n=37) had 7 to 9 years; 15% (n=45) having 10 to 12 years and remaining 2.66% (n=8) had professional experience more than 12 years. Mean value of experience of the participants was \bar{X} = 4.79 years; Standard deviation = \pm 3.0 as indicated in the (Table no. 4.1. & figure no. 4.2.).

As per the qualification of the respondents 27.33% (n=82) having diploma in general nursing whereas 57.66% (n=173) had Post RN and rest of the 15% (n=45) having generic nursing qualification indicated in the (Table no. 4.1.). There were 76.66% (n=230) participants working in ICU; 18.33% (n=55) working in emergency and only 5% (n=15) working in general wards of the Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore.

Table 4.1. Demographic data of the participants

Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%age)
Gender		
Male	0	0.00
Female	300	100.00
Total	300	100.00
Age		
21-30 years	146	48.66
31-40 years	75	25.00
41-50 years	65	21.66
51-60 years	14	4.66
Total	300	100.00
Mean = \bar{X} = 35.61 years; standard deviation = \pm 9.0		
Qualification		
Diploma in general nursing	82	27.33
Post RN	173	57.66
Generic nursing	45	15
Total	300	100.00
Religion		
Islam	285	95
Christian	12	4
other	3	1
Total	300	100.00
Experience		
1-3 years	80	26.66
4-6 years	130	43.33

7-9 years	37	12.33
10-12 years	45	15
12+ years	8	2.66
Total	300	100
Mean = \bar{X} = 4.79 years; standard deviation = \pm 3.0		
Department		
ICU	230	76.66
Emergency	55	18.33
General ward	15	5
Total	300	100.00
Duty shift		
Morning	163	54.33
Evening	75	25.00
Night	62	20.66
Total	300	100.00

Figure 4.1. Age of the participants

Figure 4.2. Professional experience of the participants

Total 300 nurses recruited in the study conducted at Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore regarding assessment of knowledge and practices of catheter associated urinary tract infection among nurses. Self-structured questionnaires were used to collect the data from the participants and as per the knowledge of the respondents only 45% (n=135) knew that most common hospital acquired infection was CAUTI and rest of 55% (n=165) didn't know as indicated in the (Table no. 4.2.).

In the sample of 300 participants, 65.66% (n=197) replied that risk factor of CAUTI was not directly related to the duration of catheterization. Only 34.33% (n=103) replied the right answer whereas 51.33% (n=154) knew that high risk group of CAUTI included female gender and elderly patients and remaining 48.66% (n=146) didn't know as shown in the (Table no. 4.2.).

48.66% (n=146) knew that catheter must be removed as soon as possible or within 24 hours for catheterized post-operative patients and remaining

51.33% (n=154) replied negatively. In the sample of 300 respondents only 45.65% (n=42) knew that CAUTI increases the duration of the patients stay in the hospital and 54.35% (n=50) didn't as mentioned in the (Table no. 4.2.).

Only 300 participants appeared in the study in the population of 12 nurses out of which 55% (n=165) knew that if urinary catheter remain indwelling for a month the risk of bacteriuria was high and 45% (n=135) didn't know the accurately. Even 54.33% (n=163) didn't know that silicone alloy-coated indwelling urinary catheters may benefit the patients for long term care and remaining 46.74% (n=43) correctly responded as indicated in the (Table no. 4.2.).

There were total 300 participants included in the study out of which only 39.13% (n=36) knew that CAUTI was most caused by Escherichia coli and remaining 60.87% (n=56) didn't know recorded in the (Table no. 4.2.). Overall, poor knowledge found among the participants regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection.

Table 4.2. Assessment of knowledge of nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI)

Questions	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Most common hospital acquired infection is CAUTI.	Yes	135	45
	No	165	55
Total		300	100.00
Risk factor of CAUTI is not directly related to the duration of catheterization.	Yes	197	65.66
	No	103	34.33
Total		300	100.00
High risk group of CAUTI include female gender and elderly patients.	Yes	154	51.33
	No	146	48.66
Total		300	100.00
Acute urinary retention and bladder obstruction is the indication of catheterization.	Yes	197	65.66
	No	103	34.33
Total		300	100.00
Strict aseptic precautions to be followed for urinary catheterization.	Yes	39	42.39
	No	53	57.61
Total		300	100.00
Catheter must be remove as soon as possible or within 24 hours for catheterized post operative patients.	Yes	146	48.66
	No	154	51.33
Total		300	100.00
Cleaning the pre urethral region with antiseptics is mandatory to prevent CAUTI.	Yes	39	42.39
	No	53	57.61
Total		300	100.00
Secure the IUC catheter properly after insertion, to prevent replacement of the catheter and injury to the bladder.	Yes	40	43.48
	No	52	56.52
Total		300	100.00
CAUTI increases the duration of the patients stay in the hospital.	Yes	42	45.65
	No	50	54.35
Total		300	100.00
If urinary catheter remain indwelling for a month the risk of bacteriuria is high.	Yes	165	55
	No	135	45

Total		300	100.00
Silicone alloy-coated indwelling urinary catheters may benefit the patients for long term care.	Yes	43	46.74
	No	163	54.33
Total		300	100.00
Frequent use of lubricants with antiseptics may not be necessary.	Yes	60	65.22
	No	32	34.78
Total		300	100.00
Daily cleaning of the meatus and catheter with soap and water reduce the possibility of CAUTI.	Yes	44	47.83
	No	48	52.17
Total		300	100.00
CAUTI is most often caused by Escherichia coli.	Yes	36	39.13
	No	56	60.87
Total		300	100.00

Regarding the causes of medical errors in CAUTI among nurses only 43.48% (n=40) agreed that before and after handling the catheter site, hands must be washed with antiseptics whereas 38.04% (n=35) disagreed and 18.33% (n=55) gave neutral reply as shown in the (Table no. 4.3.).

In the sample of 300 participants only 46.74% (n=43) agreed that appropriate catheter size should be used to minimize urethral trauma; 36.96% (n=34) respondents were disagreed and 12.33% (n=37) were nor agreed not disagreed with the statement.

Total 300 participants appeared in the study out of which 46.74% (n=43) agreed that urinary catheterization must be done whenever there was an appropriate indication whereas 29.35% (n=55)

disagreed and remaining 23.91% (n=22) gave neutral response. Even only 48.66% (n=146) agreed that urine collection bag should be empty regularly and remaining 51.33% (n=154) were not agreed and some gave neutral respond as revealed in the (Table no. 4.3.).

As 300 patients included in the study and 34.78% (n=32) agreed that isolation for a patient was necessary while rest of the 65.22% (n=60) were not agreed. Out of 300 participants only 42.39% (n=39) agreed that maintaining close drainage system prevents CAUTI whereas remaining 57.61% (n=53) didn't as shown in the (Table no. 4.3.). Overall, inadequate practices regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection found among the participants.

Table 4.3. Assessment of causes of errors regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI)

Questions	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Before and after handling the catheter site, hands must be washed with antiseptics.	Strongly Disagree	75	25.00
	Disagree	45	15
	Neutral	55	18.33
	Agree	30	32.61
	Strongly agree	14	4.66
Total		300	100.00
Appropriate catheter size should be used to minimize urethral trauma.	Strongly Disagree	45	15
	Disagree	22	23.91

	Neutral	37	12.33
	Agree	75	25.00
	Strongly agree	62	20.66
Total		300	100.00
Urinary catheterization must be done whenever there is an appropriate indication.	Strongly Disagree	11	11.96
	Disagree	16	17.39
	Neutral	22	23.91
	Agree	21	22.83
	Strongly agree	22	23.91
Total		300	100.00
Twisting and kinking of the catheter must be prevented for an unobstructed flow of urine.	Strongly Disagree	55	18.33
	Disagree	22	23.91
	Neutral	65	21.66
	Agree	27	29.35
	Strongly agree	45	15
Total		300	100.00
At least once a daily the bladder must be irrigated with antimicrobial solutions.	Strongly Disagree	9	9.78
	Disagree	18	19.57
	Neutral	11	11.96
	Agree	130	43.33
	Strongly agree	21	22.83
Total		300	100.00
Urine collection beg should be empty regularly.	Strongly Disagree	65	21.66
	Disagree	65	21.66
	Neutral	19	20.65
	Agree	80	26.66
	Strongly agree	21	22.83
Total		300	100.00
Urine collection beg must be positioned and fixed below the level of the bladder.	Strongly Disagree	21	22.83
	Disagree	13	14.13
	Neutral	37	12.33
	Agree	75	25.00
	Strongly agree	62	20.66
Total		300	100.00
Isolation must be done for a patient with UTI,	Strongly Disagree	9	9.78

from other non-infected patients.	Disagree	65	21.66
	Neutral	37	40.22
	Agree	14	4.66
	Strongly agree	22	23.91
Total		300	100.00
Maintaining close drainage systems to prevents CAUTI.	Strongly Disagree	16	17.39
	Disagree	65	21.66
	Neutral	75	25.00
	Agree	29	31.52
	Strongly agree	14	4.66
Total		300	100.00
Regular educational training to be given on basic urinary catheter care.	Strongly Disagree	2	2.17
	Disagree	12	4
	Neutral	2	2.17
	Agree	44	47.83
	Strongly agree	135	45
Total		300	100.00

There were 300 participants appeared in the study held at Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection and chi-square test was performed to check the association between the variables. As per the knowledge of the participants regarding CAUTI, age of the participants had direct impact on the knowledge as chi-square test showed value= $X^2=1.000$; p-value= 0.003 ($p<0.05$). It revealed that older participants having good knowledge as compared to the younger ones as well as adequate practices and chi-square value $X^2=1.000$; p-value= 0.007 ($p<0.05$) shown in the (Table no. 4.4.).

There was direct association between the professional experience of the participants and knowledge regarding CAUTI as chi-square test recorded the value = $X^2=1.000$; p-value=0.000 ($p<0.05$). As well as professional experience had direct impact on the practices of the participants

determined the chi-square test value $X^2=1.000$; p-value= 0.000 ($p<0.05$). It revealed that participants with higher experience having good knowledge and adequate practices as compared to less experienced respondents as indicated in the (Table no. 4.4.).

Total 300 nurses included in the study and department of the participants having significant association regarding knowledge of CAUTI. Chi-square test was performed to check the association between the variables. It showed the value = $X^2=1.000$; p-value=0.000 ($p<0.05$). It disclosed that participants who were working in ICU having good knowledge and adequate practices as compared to others as mentioned in the (Table no. 4.4.). Overall, age, professional experience and working found significant association on knowledge and practices of the participants.

Table 4.4. Association of demographic data of the participants with the knowledge and practice of nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI)

Variables	Knowledge		Practices	
	Good	Poor	Adequate	Inadequate
Age				
21-30 years	15	30	20	25
31-40 years	12	11	12	11
41-50 years	10	4	10	4
51-60 years	5	5	5	5
Total	300			
X²=1.000; p-value= 0.003			X²=1.000; p-value= 0.007	
Experience				
1-3 years	8	16	2	22
4-6 years	12	21	11	22
7-9 years	12	3	15	0
10-12 years	9	3	11	1
12+ years	7	1	6	2
Total	300			
X²=1.000; p-value= 0.000			X²=1.000; p-value= 0.000	
Department				
ICU	40	28	33	35
Emergency	7	10	10	7
General ward	2	5	2	5
Total	300			
X²=1.000; p-value= 0.000			X²=1.000; p-value= 0.000	

***Significant p<0.05**

Overall result findings showed that 45.65.50% participants having good knowledge and remaining 54.35% had poor. In contrast, 48.66% participants reported adequate practices and 51.33% had inadequate practices as

mentioned in the (Figure no. 4.3.). Finally, insufficient knowledge and inadequate practices found among the nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection.

Figure 4.3. Percentages of knowledge and practices among nurses regarding CAUTI

5.1. DISCUSSION:

Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) constitute major public health problems worldwide; among which Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTIs) are the most common. Current study was conducted to assess knowledge and practices among nurses regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection at Punjab Institute of Neurosciences Hospital, Lahore. There were 1200 nurses appeared in the research and 300 considered for the study and rest of the nurses excluded as they didn't meet the criterion of the study. In the population of 1200 nurses only 300 female participants included in the study having age 21 years old to 60 years old. 48.66% (n=146) having age group (21-30) years; 25.00% (n=75) belonged to (31-40) years; 21.66% (n=65) had an age group of (41-50) years and remaining 4.66% (n=14) belonged to (51-60) years old. Mean age of the participants was \bar{X} = 35.61 years old; Standard deviation = \pm 9.0 as depicted in the (Table no. 4.1. & figure no. 4.1.).

Findings of our study in accordance with the research work of (Jacqueline Mukakamanzi, 2017) who carried out a research in Rawanda and found that knowledge among nurses regarding CAUTI was unsatisfactory as in our study it is also determined that participants having poor knowledge. Our research also agreed with the research work of (K.C. et al., 2021) who administered an analytical cross-sectional study in Nepal in which total 160 staff nurses were selected using a probability simple random

sampling technique. They found that majority of nurse's level of knowledge was not satisfactory regarding CAUTI prevention. Age, professional qualification, designation, area of practice were statistically significant with the level of knowledge.

In our study findings, age, working experience and unit of working had significant association with the knowledge and practices of the participants resembles with the findings of (Algarni et al., 2019) performed a descriptive cross-sectional study in which 137 nurses recruited from medical and intensive care units in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. As they determined there was a significant relation between nurses knowledge and age and there was a significant relation between nurses practices and current unit. In our study, participants who were working in ICU having better knowledge and practices as compared to others.

Our study findings revealed that respondents have poor knowledge and inadequate practices regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection had direct association with the research findings of (Teshager et al., 2022) carried out a descriptive cross-section study in Ethiopia in which 204 nurses of ICU department included and found nurses' knowledge and practice towards the prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infection was relatively poor. Professional work experience had a significant statistical association with the level of knowledge.

Our result also showed that silicone was better than others in reducing the encrustation risk as apparent from the research work of (Gould et al., 2017). In the current study it is reported that nurses were less knowledgeable regarding prevention of CAUTI as (Opina & Oducado, 2014) determined in their research work that there was a great number of nurses unknowledgeable regarding prevention of CAUTI which might lead to mistakes and negligence in IUC care which in turn might cause a great risk in getting CAUTI for patients during their hospitalization.

Our study verified the research work of (Rashmi KC, Dhakal B., 2021) who showed that shortening the duration of catheterization, avoiding unnecessary catheterization, preparing and implementing standard infections control protocols and using sterile precautions in the insertion and maintenance of indwelling urinary catheters could reduce catheter-related complications.

Our study revealed that there was direct association of spread of CAUTI and antiseptic is contradicted with the research findings of (Mitchell et al., 2011) who carried out a research work and reported that there was no significant difference between antiseptic lubricants and non-antiseptic lubricants in preventing CAUTI (Catheter Urinary Tract Infection), despite the fact there was very low-quality evidence advising to use lubricants during indwelling urinary catheter insertion to decrease the risk of CAUTI.

Many researchers recommended increasing the knowledge of nurses through appropriate educational programs and training may prevent the CAUTI but researchers didn't determine the type of training should be effective and efficient to enhance the knowledge among study participants. As from financial accounting perspectives, every human action should be cost-effective in order to reduce the cost of hospital and healthcare department. From personnel trainings we always measure the following outcomes e.g., reaction, learning, behaviour and results and not every training brings optimum results, it depends on the aptitude and leadership style of the trainer. It's really a matter of discussion but we wind up the conversation by saying this hospital administration must take immediate steps to improve the knowledge and practices among nurses regarding CAUTI.

5.2. CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, lack of knowledge found among the study participants regarding catheter associated urinary tract infection. As compared to knowledge practices regarding CAUTI were little bit better among respondents. Age, professional experience,

working unit had direct association with the knowledge and practices of study participants. Overall, lack of knowledge and poor practices reported among the nurses of hospital may cause to increase the LOS (length of stay) and cost of not only the hospital but also healthcare department of the Pakistan.

5.3. Recommendations

- ◆ Periodic workshops should be conducted by the hospital as well as healthcare commission of the Pakistan to upgrade the knowledge of health care workers regarding infection control and prevention.
- ◆ Hospital administration should take affirmative actions to enhance the practices of CAUTI because not only knowledge is necessary but also practices are mandatory too to overcome the catheter associated urinary tract infection.
- ◆ Disseminate health related awareness among the Pakistani nation regarding diseases and its prevention because without the contribution of public we can't control the infections and possible remedies for its preventions.

REFERENCES:

1. Martin J. (2012). Registered nurses' practices and perceptions of indwelling urinary catheters and number of indwelling urinary catheter days in a hospitalized population.
2. Zegeye AF, Kassahun CW, Temechu YZ (2021). Knowledge, practice and associated factors of catheter-associated urinary tract infection prevention among nurses working at University of Gondar Comprehensive Special-ized Hospital, Northwest Ethiopia.
3. Haza'a AA, Al-Jaradi A, Odhah MA (2021). Knowledge of nurses toward prevention for catheter-associated urinary tract infection in public hospitals at Amran City, Yemen. *Open J Nurs.*;11:933-46.
4. Prasanna K, Radhika M (2015). Knowledge regarding catheter care among staff nurses. *Int J Appl Res.*;1:182-6.
5. Talaat M, El-Shokry M, El-Kholy J, Ismail G, Kotb S, Hafez S, et al. (2016). National surveillance of healthcare-associated infections in Egypt: developing a sustainable program in a resource-limited country. *Am J Infect Control* ;44:1296-301.
6. Scott RD. (2016). The direct medical costs of healthcare-associated infections in US hospitals and the benefits of prevention.
7. Weber DJ, Sickbert-Bennett EE, Gould CV, Brown VM, Huslage K, Rutala WA. (2011). Incidence of catheter-associated and non-catheter-associated urinary tract infections in

- a healthcare system. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol*;32:822–3.
8. Ashraf F, Iram S, Rasheed F, Shaukat M. (2015). Comparison Between Non-Catheterized And Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infections Caused By Extended Spectrum B-Lactamase Producing Escherichia Coli And Klebsiella Pneumoniae. *BioRxiv.* ;4(4):019026.
 9. Algarni SS, Sofar SSS, Wazqar DY. (2019). Nurses' knowledge and practices toward prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infection at king Abdulaziz University Hospital. *J Health Med Nurs.*;4:50–73.
 10. Gould CV, Umscheid CA, Agarwal RK, Kuntz G, Pegues DA. (2009). Guideline for prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infections.
 11. Rashmi KC, Dhakal B. (2021). Knowledge, attitude and practice on prevention of catheter-associated UTI among nurses of a tertiary care hospital. *J Coll Med Sci Nepal.* 2021;17:61–8.
 12. Banks, H., Abdella, R., & Willmann, Y. (2016). Nursing Interventions Aimed at Reducing the Incidence of Hospital Acquired Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections.
 13. Al Nasser, W., El-saed, A., Al-jardani, A., Althaqafi, A., Alansari, H., Alsalman, J, Balkhy, H. H. (2016). American Journal of Infection Control rates of catheter-associated urinary tract infection in tertiary care hospitals in 3 Arabian Gulf countries : A 6-year surveillance study. *American Journal of Infection Control*, 44(12), 1589–1594.
 14. Shehab, M.S. (2017). Impact of protocol of care of patients undergoing urinary catheterization. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 10(2), 1013–1021.
 15. Sobeih, H.S., & Nasr, M.H. (2015). Indwelling urinary catheter management: Effect of an interactive workshop on nurses' practice and perception. *New York Science Journal*, 8(5), 117–126.
 16. Opina, M.L.F., & Oducado, R.M.F. (2014). Infection control in the use of urethral catheters : Knowledge and practices of nurses in a private hospital in Iloilo city, Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences, 1(5), 93–100.
 17. Mukakamanzi, J. (2017). Knowledge, attitude and practices of nurses towards the prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infection in selected Referral Hospitals in Rwanda. (Doctoral dissertation).
 18. Tenke, P., Mezei, T., Bode, I., & Köves, B. (2017). Catheter-associated urinary tract infections. *European Urology, Supplements*, 16(4), 138–143.
 19. Parker, V., Giles, M., Graham, L., Suthers, B., Watts, W., O'Brien, T., & Searles, A. (2017). Avoiding inappropriate urinary catheter use and catheter-associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI): A pre-post control intervention study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 17(1), 314.
 20. Gaid, E., Assiri, A., McNabb, S., & Banjar, W. (2017). Device-associated nosocomial infection in general hospitals, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 2013-2016. *Journal Epidemiology and Global Health*, 1589-1594.
 21. Opina, M.L.F., & Oducado, R.M.F. (2014). Infection control in the use of urethral catheters : Knowledge and practices of nurses in a private hospital in Iloilo city, Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences, 1(5), 93–100.
 22. Gould, C.V., Umscheid, C.A., Agarwal, R.K., Kuntz, G., Pegues, D. A., & Healthcare Infection Control Practices Advisory Committee. (2017). Guideline for prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infections 2009. *Infection Control and Hospital Epidemiology*, 31(4), 319-26. doi: 10.1086/651091.
 23. Shah, M., Wahab, F., Ullah, F., Gul, U., Aziz, A., & Ullah, Z. (2017). Infection control in the use of urethral catheter: Knowledge and practices of nurses. *American Journal of Advanced Drug Delivery*, 5(1), 1-8.
 24. Mitchell, B., Ware, C., McGregor, A., Brown, S., Wells, A., Stuart, R.L., Mason, M. (2011). ASID (HICSIG)/AICA position statement: Preventing catheter-associated urinary tract infections in patients. *Healthcare Infection*, 16(2), 45-52.
 25. Gesmundo, M. (2016). Managing indwelling urinary catheters. *Kai Tiaki Nursing New Zealand*, 22(6), 14-15.
 26. Loveday, H.P., Wilson, J.A., Pratt, R.J., Golsorkhi, M., Tingle, A., Bak, A., Wilcox, M. (2014). National Evidence-Based Guidelines for preventing healthcare-associated infections in NHS Hospitals in England. *Journal of Hospital Infection*, 86(S1), S1–S70. doi: 10.1016/S0195-6701(13)60012-2.
 27. Kose, Y., Leblebici, Y., Akdere, S.S., Cakmakci, H., & Otunctemur, S., Egici, M.T., & Bektumur, G. (2016). Level of knowledge of the nurses work in a public hospital about the prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infections. *The Medical Bulletin of Sisli Etfal Hospital*, 50(1), 70-79.
 28. Mukakamanzi, J. (2017). Knowledge, attitude and practices of nurses towards the prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infection in selected Referral Hospitals in Rwanda. (Doctoral dissertation).

29. Shehzadi, A., Ali, A., Bhatti, R., & yaseen, I. (2018). Knowledge and attitude of nurses towards the prevention of catheter-associated urinary Tract Infection in ICU, S of A Public Hospital Lahore. *Saudi Journal of Nursing and Health Care*, 7921, 119–124.
30. Shehab, M.S. (2017). Impact of protocol of care of patients undergoing urinary catheterization. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 10(2), 1013–1021.
31. Lo, E., Nicolle, L.E., Mph, S.E.C., Gould, C., Mph, L.L. M., Meddings, J., Gould, C. (2016). Strategies to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract infections in acute care hospitals: update. *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology*, 35(5), 464-479.
32. Kalantarzadeh, M., Mohammadnejad, E., Ehsani, S.R., & Tamizi, Z. (2014). Knowledge and practice of nurses about the control and prevention of nosocomial infections in emergency departments. *Archives of clinical infectious diseases*, 9(4).
33. Hartley, S.E. and Valley, S.C. (2015) Prevention of Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections in the Hospital. *Hospital Medicine Clinics*, 4, 258-271.
34. Algarni, S.S., Sofar, S.M. and Wazqar, D.Y. (2019) Nurses' Knowledge and Practices toward Prevention of Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infection at King Abdulaziz University. *Journal of Health, Medicine and Nursing*, 14, 50-73.
35. Anwar, G., Nawaz, G., Afzal, M., Majeed, I. and Waqas, A. (2017) Assessment of Perceptions and Practices of the Nurses to Prevent Indwelling Catheter Associated Infection; Jinnah Hospital Lahore, Pakistan. *International Journal of Applied Sciences and Biotechnology*, 5, 150-158.
36. Benny, A.M., Idiculla, A.S., Kunjumon, A. and Sequera, S.K. (2020) Nurses' Knowledge on Prevention of Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infection in a Selected Hospital of Mangaluru. *Journal of Health and Allied Sciences NU*, 10, 128-131.
37. Teshager et al., (2022). Knowledge, practice and associated factors of nurses towards prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract infection in intensive care unit of public hospitals administered by Federal Government in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: a cross-sectional institutional-based study; *BMC Nursing* 21:186.
38. Algarni et al., (2019). *Journal of Health, Medicine and Nursing* ISSN 2520-4025 (Online) Vol.4, Issue 1 No.4, pp 39- 62.
39. K.C. et al., (2021). Knowledge, Attitude and Practice on Prevention of Catheter-Associated UTI Among Nurses of a Tertiary Care Hospital. *JCMS Nepal* ; 17(1); 61-8.
40. Jacqueline Mukakamanzi (2017). Knowledge, attitude and Practices of nurses towards the prevention of catheter-associated urinary tract Infection in selected referral hospitals in Rwanda.
41. Haza'a, A.A., Al-Jaradi, A. and Odhah, M.A. (2021). Knowledge of nurses toward prevention for catheter- associated urinary tract infection in public hospitals at Amran City, Yemen. *Open Journal of Nursing*, 11, 933-946.